

DDoS Detection in SDN using machine learning and feature selection methods

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Abstract

There are comprehensive studies on DDoS attack detection and IDS systems, but the numbers are not as considerable in SDN (Software Defined Networks). This paper compared different feature selection approaches on SDN DDoS datasets using various machine learning algorithms. We first use famous machine learning algorithms, then we use feature selection techniques to reduce the training time, and after that, we compare the results with other related studies. Our results show that pairing the Decision Tree and Genetic Algorithm works excellently in both of our datasets. We obtained the accuracy of 0.999983 and 1 using InSDN and DDoS SDN datasets, respectively. Also, the XG Boost algorithm has remarkable results, but the Decision Tree is the best when it comes to the training time, with an average training time of 0.33177 and 0.78960 using InSDN and DDoS SDN datasets, respectively.

Keywords: SDN; DDoS; Machine Learning; Feature Selection

1. Main text

Nowadays, security is vital for companies. Any second in which a company's site is out of order, they lost tons of money. Imagine not only the company's site not responding due to a DDoS attack, but also a ransomware has encrypted all the files in the server. That's why security is so crucial for companies, and it is imperative to use tools to prevent these incidents.

1.1. DoS Attacks

In literature, DoS is a kind of attack in which an attacker makes a machine or network resource unavailable to its users. From a high level, a DoS attack is like Black Friday sales, when thousands of users are clamouring for a bargain, often causing a denial of service. DDoS attacks happen when lots of internet-connected computers do a DoS attack at the same time. These computers could be infected via malware and the attacker can control them remotely. These computers are called bots or zombies, and a group of these computers is called a botnet. An attacker can connect to a botnet and order them to attack a victim by sending a command remotely see Fig. 2. Since every bot is a legitimate network user separating them is a tricky task. We can divide DDoS attacks into three main categories, Application layer attacks, Protocol attacks, and Volumetric attacks.

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Fig. 1. DDoS attack.

1.1.1. Application layer attacks

Application layer attacks take place in layer 7 of the OSI model. Its goal is to exhaust the target's resources. One of the famous Application layer attacks is HTTP flood. It is similar to repeatedly pressing a refresh button in a web browser on many different computers. As a result, many HTTP requests flood the server, see Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. HTTP Flood attack.

1.1.2. Protocol attacks

Protocol attacks are usually included in layers 3 and 4 of the OSI model. These attacks intend to exhaust network services. A famous attack in this category is SYN flood attack. A SYN Flood occurs when an attacker sends many TCP SYN requests to a server to establish a three-way handshake and open a port for starting a connection. As a result, the attacker opens many ports in the victim's computer, and when there are no other ports available, a legitimate request drops, and actual users cannot connect to the server (see Fig. 3). This attack exploits the TCP handshake. The attacker sends TCP SYN packets to the victim, and the victim responds to every request, but the hacker never sends the ACK, which is the final step in a three-way handshake. This process results in exhausting the target's resources.

Fig. 3. SYN Flood attack.

1.1.3. Volumetric attacks

Volumetric attacks are kinds of attacks in which an attacker attempts to create congestion by consuming all available bandwidth between the target and the Internet. This kind of attack focuses on consuming all the bandwidth of the victim. Attackers usually use some form of amplification to generate a huge amount of traffic. One form of these attacks is DNS Amplification, which a hacker sends a request to a public DNS resolver via a spoofed IP address that belongs to the victim, and then the DNS server responds to the victim with a lengthy request (see Fig. 4). These attacks could be carried out with a botnet, resulting in a huge amount of data that exhausts the target's resources.

Fig. 4. DNS Amplification attack.

1.2. SDN

Software-Defined Networking (SDN) is a new point of view on networking. Using software and application programming interface (API) to interact with hardware infrastructure. This model differs from traditional networks, which use dedicated hardware devices (i.e., routers and switches) to control network traffic. SDN can create and manage a virtual network or control traditional hardware via software. SDN enables dynamic, programmatically

efficient network configuration to improve network performance and monitoring, making it more like cloud computing than traditional network management. It addresses the static architecture of conventional networks. It attempts to centralize network intelligence in one network component by disassociating the forwarding process of network packets (data plane) from the routing process (control plane). The control plane has some controllers, which we can think of as the SDN network's brain. The biggest cons of SDN networks is the centralization, which involves us to the security and scalability of this centralized network which opens some unique attacks specific to SDN networks. These attacks can occur in the SDN controller or communication channels between the control and data plane devices. There are various categories of attacks on SDN. Attacks on the data plane, attacks on the control plane, attacks on the SDN controller, and attacks on the application plane.

1.2.1. Attacks on the data plane

An attacker can compromise the network nodes, and the attacker can gain unauthorized access to hosts, and generate a massive DDoS attack.

1.2.2. Attacks on the control plane

In SDN each device has a channel with the controller, but physically they all use the same channel which has been separated logically. If an attacker can break the trust between controller and data plane using a flood attack it can disconnect controller from the network and then the attacker can establish a trust with OpenFlow switches [1] and the controller to launch various type of attacks like man in the middle and sniffing the traffic.

1.2.3. Attacks on SDN controller

The controller is the main component of the SDN, and it has an operating system. Attackers can use their vulnerabilities to control the network traffic by creating new policies and gaining control over SDN.

1.2.4. Attacks on the application plane

An exploit of application vulnerability could cause malfunction, disruption of service, or eavesdropping of data, letting the attacker bypass the firewall and IDS. The attacker could gain access with a high privilege to an SDN application and perform illegal operations. The popularity of SDN opens a new research field to prevent network attacks in this kind of network. In this paper, we will use machine learning algorithms to detect DDoS attacks in SDN.

1.3. Feature selection

Network flow datasets have many features, and handling them consumes lots of resources; hence we use feature selection algorithms to train the classifier faster and make it more precise. There are many feature selection algorithms, but generally, they are classified under four categories: Filter Methods, Wrapper Methods, Embedded Methods, and Hybrid Methods.

1.3.1. Filter methods

Filter methods measure the relevance of features by their correlation with the dependent variable, and they use statistical methods to evaluate a subset of features. Some famous Filter Methods are Chi-square, Fisher's score, Correlation coefficient, Variance threshold, and Mean absolute difference.

1.3.2. Wrapper Methods

Wrapper Methods measure the best features by training them on a cross-validation model. That is why they are costly in terms of resources. Some examples of these methods are Forward feature selection, Backward feature elimination, Exhaustive feature selection, and Recursive feature elimination (RFE).

1.3.3. Embedded methods

Embedded methods encompass the benefits of both the wrapper and filter methods by including interactions of features and maintaining reasonable computational cost. Two examples of these methods are LASSO regularization and Random forest importance.

1.3.4. Hybrid models

We can make a hybrid model using a mixture of algorithms with the speed advantage of Filter methods and the precise of wrapper methods. We also can use other algorithms for feature selection like PCA and Genetic Algorithm. This paper uses the Correlation coefficient, PCA, genetics, and RFE.

2. Related Works

In recent years, researchers have put much effort into detecting anomalies using classical machine learning and deep neural networks algorithms. In this section, we review some of these works.

Bawany et al. proposed a novel SDN-based proactive DDoS Defense Framework (ProDefense) for a smart city data centre. Their proposed method allowed the implementation of application-specific requirements for DDoS attack detection [2]. Mousavi et al. used the central control of SDN for attack detection. They introduced an effective and lightweight solution for its resources [3]. Elsayed et al. proposed a new SDN dataset called InSDN [4]. Perez-Diaz et al. used machine learning algorithms like J48, Random Tree, REP Tree, Random Forest, Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), and Support Vector Machines (SVM) on CIC dataset. They could detect 95% of attacks [5]. Tonkal et al. used a feature selection method to feed the output data to machine learning algorithms like kNN, Decision Tree, SVM and ANN using DDoS attack SDN [6] and InSDN [4] datasets [7].

3. Proposed Method

This section explains our method and then investigates the datasets we used; after that, we review the preprocessing steps. Finally, we describe the evaluation metrics that we used.

3.1. Our Method

In this paper, we tried to detect DDoS attacks in SDN by machine learning approaches. Classical machine learning algorithms work great with the task of classifying anomalies from benign data. In our experiments, we analyzed some classical algorithms like Decision Tree, KNN, SVM, Logistic Regression, and Naïve Bayes, along with some newer algorithms like XG Boost, Ada Boost and Random Forest algorithms. We discovered that KNN and SVM are too slow. Even though Naïve Bayes and Logistic Regression are fast, they do not get good results.

3.2. Dataset

When it comes to selecting datasets for DDoS detection in SDN, our choices are not ample. We used two widely used DDoS attack SDN [2] and InSDN [3] datasets. DDoS attack SDN has 23 features and 104,345 instances. It has two binary labels 0, 1 to show benign and DDoS attacks respectively. There are 63,561 with 0 labels and 40,784 with 1 label. InSDN dataset provide different kind of attacks data on SDN in addition to DDoS, but since our task in this paper is limited to DDoS detection we only use DDoS and benign data. There are 84 features and 116,837 instances in this dataset which consist of 68,424 normal data and 48,413 DDoS data.

3.3. Preprocessing

In our datasets, there are features that we do not use (i.e., source and destination IP, timestamp). Our data has many features; some have very high values, and some have low values. Some machine learning algorithms give higher value features, more significant weight. We use scaling to scale all the values in one range. Some features (e.g., Protocol UDP, TCP, and ICMP) has categorical value. To use them in machine learning algorithms, we encode them to numerical values. We then delete missing and duplicate values.

3.4. Evaluation

All of our experiments have been done via 10-Fold Cross-validation. Then we use the mean of 10-Folds as a result. We used many metrics to evaluate our best classifier. In addition to these metrics, we also use training time to evaluate the feature selection algorithms; it is a value in seconds.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (1)$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (2)$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (3)$$

$$F - Measure = 2 * \frac{Precision*Recall}{Precision+Recall} \quad (4)$$

$$ROC-AUC: \quad TPR = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad FPR = \frac{FP}{FP+TN} \quad (5)$$

4. Results

All of our experiments have been done via 10-Fold Cross-validation. Then we use the mean of 10-Folds as a result. We used many metrics to evaluate our best classifier. In addition to these metrics, we also use training time to evaluate the feature selection algorithm; it is a value in seconds.

Table 1. InSDN Dataset Results.

Classification Algorithm	Fit Time	Precision	Recall	F1	Accuracy	ROC-AUC
Decision Tree without feature selection	0.319249	0.999956	0.999971	0.999963	0.999957	0.999954
XG Boost without feature selection	7.544616	0.999956	0.999985	0.999971	0.999966	1.0
Random Forest without feature selection	11.356533	0.999956	0.999985	0.999971	0.999966	1.0
Decision Tree with genetic	0.033177	0.999971	1.0	0.999985	0.999983	0.999979
XG Boost with genetic	1.343364	0.999971	1.0	0.999985	0.999983	1.0
Random Forest with genetic	6.647430	0.999971	1.0	0.999985	0.999983	1.0
Decision Tree with RFE	0.033272	0.999971	0.999956	0.999963	0.999957	0.999957
XG Boost with RFE	1.231514	0.999971	0.999985	0.999978	0.999974	1.0
Random Forest with RFE	6.611708	0.999971	0.999971	0.999971	0.999966	1.0
Decision Tree with Pearson	0.048114	0.999956	0.999985	0.999971	0.999966	0.999962
XG Boost with Pearson	1.521191	0.999927	0.999985	0.999956	0.999949	0.999993
Random Forest with Pearson	6.268990	0.999971	0.999985	0.999978	0.999974	0.999979
Decision Tree with PCA	0.492397	0.999927	0.999956	0.999942	0.999932	0.999926
XG Boost with PCA	3.869543	0.999927	0.999971	0.999949	0.999940	0.999998
Random Forest with PCA	20.957673	0.999927	1.0	0.999963	0.999957	1.0

Table 2. Results using DDoS SDN dataset.

Classification Algorithm	Fit Time	Precision	Recall	F1	Accuracy	ROC-AUC
Decision Tree without feature selection	0.423405	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
XG Boost without feature selection	4.999456	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Random Forest without feature selection	20.711183	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Decision Tree with genetic	0.078960	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
XG Boost with genetic	2.435409	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Random Forest with genetic	11.008383	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Decision Tree with RFE	0.085595	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
XG Boost with RFE	2.555164	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Random Forest with RFE	12.192469	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Decision Tree with Pearson	0.138890	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
XG Boost with Pearson	2.649833	0.997732	0.999136	0.998433	0.998777	0.999976
Random Forest with Pearson	15.629742	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Decision Tree with PCA	0.412745	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
XG Boost with PCA	4.584461	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Random Forest with PCA	20.558340	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0

Table 3. Comparing results with[4] and [7].

Related Work and Dataset	Fit Time	Precision	Recall	F1	Accuracy	ROC-AUC
InSDN A Novel SDN Intrusion Dataset	41.503	0.999992	0.999951	0.999971	-	-
Our best result using InSDN	0.033177	0.999971	1.0	0.999985	0.999983	0.999979
Machine Learning Approach Equipped with Neighbourhood Component	-	0.9994	-	0.9985	0.9982	-
Our best result using DDoS SDN dataset	0.078960	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0

5. Discussion

As we can see in Table 1 and Table 2 Decision Tree and Genetic algorithm have almost the best results in both datasets. The training time is very smaller compared to other algorithms. Table 3 shows how good pairing of the Decision Tree and Genetic algorithm works, when we compare the results with other papers. Decision Tree not only works great with Genetic algorithm but when we look at other feature selection algorithms, we see how significantly better works in the matter of training time. The training time becomes valuable when we have a very big real-world dataset. In future works, we can use bigger datasets to see whether Decision Tree can do a great performance on big datasets or not.

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